

Development of High-Performance $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3$ Heterostructures for Electronic Devices

Never Stand Still

Faculty of Engineering

Materials Science and Engineering

A/Prof Hailong Hu

Central South University, Changsha, China

School of Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering

School of Materials Science & Engineering

UNSW Sydney, Australia

Acknowledgement

Prof Yuping Zeng, Dr. Danyang Wang, Prof Sean Li, Prof Chun Wang

Research Areas

Structure-function integrated ceramics

Oxide electronics

Function design

1. Structural ceramics—Microstructure design, preparation, mechanical property
2. Multi-functionalisation of structural ceramics (solid-gas filter, flame retardant, electronics)
3. Integration-functional ceramics and structural ceramics

Outline

- **Recent Advances and Challenges**
- **High Performance LAO/STO heterostructures**
 - The influence of growing conditions on the physical and magnetic properties of LAO/STO heterostructures
 - Role of magnetic ordering and scattering in the occurred 2DEG of LAO/STO heterostructures
 - Effect of structure arrangements, polar field and carrier effective mass on the electrical property (electron density and mobility) of LAO/STO heterostructures
 - The effect of substrate orientation and band structures on achieving the high performance LAO/STO heterostructures
- **Conclusions**

A Global and Growing Microprocessor Market

- A microprocessor is a processing unit that acts a brain in electronics devices
- Superior performance of microprocessors led to their application in computers Smartphones, gaming consoles, etc.
- A compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.48% over the period 2015-2019 predicted by the technical analysts

The Big Issue

- Demand the diminished size to achieve higher speeds of signal transfer
- Problems of energy loss and dissipation brought by the reduced size
- Compromise on device shrinkage and the overall performance
- Limits of microelectronic miniaturization
- Need an alternative semiconductor material to meet the demands of global microprocessor market

Microprocessor architecture

LaAlO₃/SrTiO₃ Heterostructures

- SrTiO₃ (STO) cubic structure , lattice constant of 3.905Å , band gap of 3.2 eV
- LaAlO₃ (LAO) pseudocubic structure, lattice constant of 3.791Å, band gap of 5.6 eV
- Two-dimensional electron gas (2DEG) occurring at the interface
- Modulated physical properties by various external signals/functional overlayers

(AlO₂)⁻
(LaO)⁺
(AlO₂)⁻
(LaO)⁺
(TiO₂)⁰
(SrO)⁰
(TiO₂)⁰
(SrO)⁰

Literature Reviews

- Comparison of LAO/STO with other solid-state materials system

Materials system	LaAlO ₃ /SrTiO ₃	III-V semiconductor heterostructure	Graphene	Nanotubes	Semiconducting nanowires
Dimensionality	2D/1D	2D/1D	2D	1D	1D
Record mobility	6600	36,000,000	200,000	> 100,000	20,000
Mean free path	Hundreds of nanometers	~100 μm	~1 μm	On substrate ~10 μm	~100 nm
Typical densities	10 ¹² -10 ¹⁴ cm ⁻²	10 ¹⁰ -10 ¹² cm ⁻²	10 ⁹ -5×10 ¹² cm ⁻²	10 ³ -10 ⁸ cm ⁻²	10 ⁵ -10 ⁸ cm ⁻²
Achievable lithographic feature size	A few nanometers	~100 nm	A few nanometers (with substantially increasing disorder)	Tens of nanometers	A few nanometers
Superconductivity	T _c ~300 mK; gate tunable	No	No	No	No
Magnetism	T _c ≥ 300 K	T _c ≤ 200 K	No	No	No
Ferroelectricity	Possible	No	No	No	No
Strong lattice electron coupling	Yes	No	No	No	No
Spin-orbit coupling	Yes; a few meV; gate tunable	Yes; ~ 1 meV; gate tunable	No; a few μeV; predicted	Yes; a few μV	Yes; ~ 200 μeV

Subtle Interplay between Localized Magnetic Moment and Itinerant Electron in $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3$ Heterostructures

Aims

- Clarify the role of magnetic ordering and scattering in 2DEG
- Investigate the interaction of itinerant electrons and magnetic moments in LAO/STO heterostructures

Experiments

- LAO/STO with specific thickness was prepared by LMBE with the in-situ RHEED.

Magnetic Ordering

- Comparison of magnetic ordering for samples prepared at different oxygen partial pressures

Magnetic Scattering

- An unexpected resistance minimum discovered at ~ 10 K under a high magnetic field
- An identified anisotropic magnetoresistance affected by the high concentration of oxygen vacancies

Confirmation of Anomalous Phenomenon

- An anomalous hall resistance observed at ~ 10 K
- Electrical measurement confirmed the high concentration of oxygen vacancies

Summary

- Resistance minimum observed at 10 K with the in-plane applied magnetic field ($\geq 4\text{T}$)
- Anisotropic magnetoresistance due to the presence of magnetic scattering
- Analysis of the interaction between itinerant electrons and localized magnetic moments

Publications

- Hai-Long Hu, Rong Zeng, Anh Pham, Thiam Teck Tan, Zhigang Chen, Charlie Kong and Danyang Wang, Sean Li. Subtle Interplay between localized magnetic moments and itinerant electrons in $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3$ heterostructures. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 2016, 8, 13630-13636.

Oxygen Vacancy Dependence of Magnetic Behavior in the $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3$ Heterostructures

Aims

- Discover the origin of magnetic properties in this non-magnetic system
- Study the correlation between magnetic properties and oxygen vacancies

Experiments

- LAO/STO with specific thickness was prepared by LMBE with the in-situ RHEED.

Magnetic Properties

- M-T behaviour as a function of P_{O_2}
- Magnetic moment decreases as the measuring temperature increases

Simulations

- Spin density of LAO/STO with one O vacancy of different configurations
- Partial density of states projected on Ti atoms' d orbitals

Simulations

- The calculated total energies (eV) of LAO/STO with one O vacancy of different configurations
- Most stable oxygen vacancies are S-LAO and I-STO, which are most likely responsible for the formed ferromagnetic interaction.

	1 layer LAO	2 layers LAO	3 layers LAO	4 layers LAO
Pristine	-450.21	-528.81	-607.25	-685.69
S-LAO	-440.54	-519.11	-598.05	-676.85
B-STO-SO	-439.61	-518.20	-596.65	-675.08
B-STO-TO	-439.80	-518.33	-596.80	-675.23
I-LAO	-439.74	-518.46	-596.94	-675.30
I-STO	-439.73	-518.28	-596.91	-675.37

Summary

- Experimentally and theoretically demonstrate that the enhancement of the saturated magnetization of the LAO/STO heterostructures induced by oxygen vacancies
- Room temperature ferromagnetic behavior observed in low-pressure-grown samples
- Tuning of magnetism through changing the growth oxygen partial pressure is a feasible strategy in designing electronic devices

Publications

- Hai-Long Hu, Lei Ao, Anh Pham, Danyang Wang, Yu Wang, Zhigang Chen, Charlie Kong, Thiam Teck Tan, Xiaotao Zu and Sean Li. Oxygen vacancy dependence of magnetic behaviour in the $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3$ heterostructures. *Advanced Materials Interfaces*, 2016, 3, 1600547.

Largely Enhanced Mobility in Tri-Layered $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{LaAlO}_3$ Heterostructures

Aims

- Study the correlation of electron density and mobility with structure arrangements, polar field and carrier effective mass in LAO/STO heterostructures
- Assess the electrical performance of LAO/STO/LAO heterostructures

Experiments

- Various layered LAO/STO heterostructures fabricated
- The measurement in regards to film quality characterisation was performed

Electrical Properties

- Lowest sheet resistance observed in tri-layered heterostructures
- Largely enhanced electron mobility obtained in tri-layered heterostructures

2DEG Behavior

- 2D quantum oscillation of the conduction of tri-layered heterostructures
- Angular dependence of magnetoresistance as a function of temperature

Mechanism-Simulation

- Spin-polarized charge density and the partial density of states with the contribution of Ti's d and O's p for tri-layered and single layer configurations

Mechanism-Simulation

- Electrostatic potential and its average for a) STO/LAO structure and
- b) Tri-layered LAO/STO/LAO heterostructure.
- Enhancement of the polar field at the interface TiO_2 on the substrate, leading to further occupancy of the Ti's d_{xy} orbitals which can significantly influence the carrier concentration and mobility of the 2DEG

Mechanism-Simulation

- higher polar field demonstrated by a larger in-plane O-Ti-O bond angles distortion in the STO substrate (7uc)
- Effective mass reduces significantly for the complex heterostructures Tri-layered LAO/STO/LAO

Summary

- A greatly enhanced electron mobility of $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ was obtained in our tri-layered heterostructures
- The enhancement of the polar field which causes the reduced carrier effective mass in this tri-layered heterostructure plays a predominant role in the occurrence of largely enhanced mobility
- The high mobility of our 2EDG may open a new path for designing all oxide electronic devices with the LAO/STO heterostructures

Publications

- Hai-Long Hu, Anh Pham, Richard Tilley, Rong Zeng, Thiam Teck Tan, Charlie Kong, Danyang Wang and Sean Li. Largely enhanced mobility in triple-layer $\text{LaAlO}_3/\text{SrTiO}_3/\text{LaAlO}_3$ heterostructures. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 2018, 10, 20950-20958.

Conclusions

- Investigate the **growing conditions** on the physical and magnetic properties of LAO/STO heterostructures
- Clarification of **the role of magnetic ordering and scattering in 2DEG** to understand the electrical and magnetic behaviours of LAO/STO heterostructures.
- Search and optimize the LAO/STO heterostructures by **correlating their electron density and mobility with structure arrangements, polar field and carrier effective mass.**
- Engineer the **band structures** of LAO/STO heterostructures to harvest a linear Dirac dispersion at the K point where the conducting electrons will behave as massless particles.

Thank You